

Data platform

- Embedded edge system for local processing
- Generates standardised sensograms
- Real-time data transfer to cloud platform
- Enables visualisation, analytics and decision support for both case studies
- Designed for scalable, multi-sensor fusion and ML integration

Microfluidics & Sample Delivery

- Multi Mechanical Clumping + Microfluidics system ensures leak-free chip alignment
- Transparent PDMS/COC microfluidics optimised for optical access
- Syringe-based sample delivery validated for precision flows (0.05-2.5mL, 30-430 μ L/min)
- Integrated GUI for easy control and calibration
- Supports simultaneous dual-flow for reference/sample pairing (PTS sensor)

contact.

multilab-project.eu

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youtube.com/@MultiLabproject

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT WIEN
Vienna | Austria

European Cluster of Research projects for Environmental and Agri-food Monitoring

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Multi-modal, configurable
optical lab-on-chip
platform for low-cost
multipurpose diagnostics
& monitoring

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ECL sensor

- Dual-cell design for simultaneous assays
- Time-resolved luminescence
- Integrated Printed Circuit Board (PCB) ensures robust electrical contact
- Proven high-tight design for noise-free imaging
- Ray-tracing optimised optics for uniform illuminations and focus

PA-AWG sensor

- First plasmonic AWG integrated into a lab-on-chip system
- Four-channel spectral output images in real time
- AI-ready data structure for automated analyte classification
- Fully compatible with shared optics and microfluidics for hybrid sensing

PA-AWG: Plasmonic Augmented - Arrayed Waveguide Grating

PTS: Photothermal Spectrometry

ECL: Electrochemiluminescence

EC-QCL: External Cavity - Quantum Cascade Laser

PIC: Photonic Integrated Circuit

PTS sensor

- Dual-beam configuration
- Designed for nutrient detection in water
- Lock-in detection enhances the signal-to-noise ratio and improves measurement stability
- Shared optical path with PA-AWG
- Thermal stabilisation enhances measurement repeatability
- Fully compatible with EC-QCL laser integration

Integrated Readout System

- Hybrid optical readout system
- Synchronised multimodal acquisition with dual cameras
- Modular, compact, and mechanically robust architecture
- Real-time control of sources, detectors, and fluidics
- Seamless upgrade path for coherent phase and faster detection

